

When failure is not an option: The challenge of implementing Australian financial services regulations in organisations

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abstract

This article explores the reasons why implementing Australian Financial Services regulations in organisations is such a challenge. These challenges are important to explore, because such regulations must be implemented successfully if organisations want to continue in business. Many organisations, however, report experiencing mixed levels of success, despite spending significant time and resources on regulatory projects and compliance activities. Using a change management lens, a complex set of interconnected dynamics for regulations and organisations was identified. While many of these underlying forces were found to be in common with other types of large-scale change, a number of critical aspects, unique to implementing regulations, were high-lighted. Of particular note was the emergent nature of regulations, and that success or failure are found to be graduated and partially overlapping bands of activity, rather than precise definitions, with ambiguity particularly at more minimal levels of compliance. To address these challenges, it is suggested in this article that organisations adopt a differentiated approach to managing regulations, depending on the stage in that regulation's lifecycle. Implementation projects could also be planned over a longer timeframe to accommodate the evolution of such regulations, with assessments of the success of these programs ongoing. In addition, awareness of how these unique dynamics operate can assist compliance professionals in arguing for tailored approaches to implementing regulations for their organisation, and to support the business in achieving improved levels of success.

Introduction

For organisations operating in the Australian Financial Service (AFS) industry, failure to implement new or revised AFS regulations is not an option – even if this implementation requires significant business transformation. Organisations must implement compliance changes, and maintain regulatory operations successfully, if they want to continue in business and avoid negative consequences such as legal and financial penalties or reputational damage (Thomson Reuters 2012). This requirement is concerning when organisations frequently experience a mixed level of

success, despite spending significant time and financial resources on regulatory projects and compliance activities (Regulation Taskforce 2006; Productivity Commission 2011). The question is: Why is the implementation of AFS regulations such a challenge?

Through a change-management lens, this question is considered from an organisation-centric focus that has received less attention in the literature compared to the legal, policy, design, and regulator activities in financial services (See Black et al., 2005; Parker and Nielson, 2006; O'Brien, 2010). For the purposes of this article,

the term 'regulation' refers to AFS regulations and 'implementation' is used to also refer to maintaining the operations of regulations. First, an overview of the challenges facing organisations when implementing regulations is provided by considering the key characteristics of regulations and organisations. Then, the complex issue of defining success and failure in this context is explored. Using these insights, the implications for increasing the level of success of implementation of regulations in organisations are discussed.

Key characteristics of regulations

The type of regulations being considered within this article are those that are mandatory and imposed by the Australian Federal Government. Examples of such regulations include those required for compliance with the National Consumer Credit Protection reform (NCCP), which commenced in 2010 (Australian Securities and Investment Commission (ASIC) 2011a). While industry lobbying can result in aspects of regulations being clarified or delayed, regulations are typically run to a timetable set by the Government. Regulations can also intrude into an organisation's operating model, requiring significant transformation to business practices, thus impacting upon products, processes, technology and

task made more difficult with the increased amount of regulation, particularly post the 2008 Global Financial Crisis (GFC) (PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC) 2011; Accenture 2012; Australian Prudential Regulation Authority (APRA) 2012a).

However, these regulations are not necessarily rigid and prescribed because the new laws that underpin regulations are untested. Additionally, they can be interpreted in a number of different ways, and do not cover all situations. Amendments can be made to clarify the laws and refine regulations. Often, such amendments are based on feedback from industry, meaning that regulations are emergent with design and implementation running in parallel (Black 2002; Hackman 2007). Amendments can continue after regulations come into effect, particularly if they do not deliver intended benefits, or result in unintended consequences (Bookstaber 2007). Adding to the emergent nature of regulations is an inherent ambiguity in their operation. Rules-based regulations cannot cover every situation that can occur; principle-based regulations are open to interpretation; and methods for assessing effective implementation can evolve over time (Downer 2008; Mullins 2008; O'Brien 2010; Coyle 2012). This means that organisations have a level of discretion when deciding how they will interpret the rules, or principles, in order to make them work for their organisation (Hofmann 2008).

Organisations must implement compliance changes, and maintain regulatory operations successfully, if they want to continue in business and avoid negative consequences such as legal and financial penalties or reputational damage.

Furthermore, regulations are managed by a number of different regulatory agencies (Department of Finance and Deregulation 2012). This means organisations may have to deal with a range of regulatory agencies, all of which require different types of responses and processes to implement regulations. Given this complexity, regulations do not have a track record of being easy to implement, often resulting in higher costs and requiring subsequent remediation projects (Regulation Taskforce 2006; Productivity Commission 2010). Yet, the Government depends on organisations, as its agents, to implement regulations successfully for

the intent of the reform to be delivered.

Key characteristics of organisations

While the types and sizes of organisation required to implement regulations are varied, there are some common characteristics that can be considered for this discussion. For instance, the amount and pace of change for these organisations has increased

skills. It can also include the structure and culture of an organisation. Such changes are both costly and time-consuming, potentially impacting on relationships with customers, the wider economy and other industries (Hackman 2006; Baldwin et al. 2012). This intrusiveness has increased over the last decade, with regulatory agencies looking for 'genuine compliance' (Coyle 2012; Thomson Reuters 2012). This means organisations are expected to undertake more than minimal compliance, a

exponentially in recent years, due to pressures from changing markets, new technology requiring nimble business responses and a greater amount of both AFS specific and more general business regulation to implement (Morgan & Page 2008; Drezensky et al. 2012; Tandulwadikar 2012). As a result, there is competition for change resources within organisations. In the current climate, few change resources are being diverted to regulatory implementation activities (PwC 2011).

However, even when resources are made available, it is not simple to undertake these regulatory implementation activities. Such projects require large-scale change programs, involving a range of internal stakeholders (Kotter & Cohen 2002; Hackman 2005; Palmer et al. 2006; McFillen et al. 2012). Resistance from stakeholders, usual in all change, is amplified when implementing regulations (Hackman, 1999; Mento et al., 2002; Atkinson, 2005; van Dijk, 2009). The emergent nature of regulations typically creates frustrations, as plans must change, often increasing costs and reducing productivity. The mandatory nature and low confidence intended benefits will be delivered, often increases this resistance. Nor can agreement necessarily be reached as to how the implementation should be approached (Weick & Quinn 1999; Bolman & Deal 2008; Nasim & Sushil 2011). Instead, there can be a range of different perspectives from internal stakeholders about which issues are most important and what comprises success.

For instance, the CEO may regard corporate reputation issues as most important, while the business or line manager may be more concerned about keeping the business running smoothly. Frontline employees, who may be change-weary, just want to know what to do. Similarly, other areas of the business will have their perspective and particular concerns. These different perspectives can be positive, because they prompt conversations about new ways of organising and indicate that people are not disengaged (McClellan 2011; Piderit 2000). However, they can also lead to unpopular compromises and trade-offs. Despite these challenging dynamics, organisations do engage and implement regulations, even though their methods may vary.

Recent research investigating the implementation of new and revised regulations found that organisations do vary in their typical approach from a more minimalistic, reactive response, to a more comprehensive proactive response, reflecting the level of activity undertaken (Hackman 2009a, 2009b). One key finding in a report undertaken on the AFS industry was that an organisation's level of success with previous regulatory implementations was the major influence on that organisation's response. Thus, if the previous implementation was more successful, the organisation will be subsequently more proactive and do more when

next implementing regulations. Conversely, if the previous implementation was less successful, then the organisation will be more reactive and do less when next implementing regulations. The implication for organisations reporting a mixed level of success is that they may decrease their efforts to be proactive when implementing regulations because of these experiences.

These findings are consistent with change literature regarding the impact of poor change experiences and the influence of leaders and managers in encouraging certain behaviours in change implementation (Pettigrew et al. 2001; Bordia et al. 2011; Dalton 2007; Uhl-Ben et al. 2007). In this context, poor change experiences become part of an organisation's memory, prompting resistance to subsequent regulatory change initiatives. These findings also link the impact of positive experiences to creating readiness for change, and to where leaders and managers can support the adoption of positive attitudes into the culture and influence 'the way things are done around here' (Armenakis et al. 2002; Armenakis & Harris 2009). The result is that people are more ready to engage with subsequent regulatory change initiatives. Therefore, reactions to implementing regulations, whether positive or negative, contribute to creating an organisation's compliance culture.

Why implementing regulations is such a challenge

These key challenges for implementing regulations in organisations are summarised in Figure 1 and highlight the competing pressures, complexity and resource-hungry nature of these types of change initiatives.

But are these challenges, in this regulatory context, so unique? Many are shared by other types of large-scale change initiatives. For example, during the 1990s, publishers globally had to move to digital publishing models in order to continue operating in the industry (Martin & Tian 2010). There was competition for scarce change resources, as these technological changes were implemented while organisations also continued business-as-usual activities and other business development projects. These changes intruded into the functioning of many organisations, as well as impacting on the delivery of products and services, and customer relationships. This required many compromises, with many different points of view needing to be reconciled. Due to the untested nature of these technological changes, there was ambiguity about what to implement, requiring costly revisions as organisations sought to achieve their desired outcomes. These complex and resource-hungry changes have continued, with newspapers now required to be available in many digital, as well as paper, formats (INSEAD 2007; Wharton School of the University of Pennsylvania 2013).

Figure 1: The dynamics of implementing regulations in organisations

However, despite similarities, there are unique aspects that make the implementation of regulations even more challenging. The Government imposes regulations on organisations, which also captures customers who are required to use the new products or services. The Government has the ability to penalise organisations, if they fail to achieve appropriate implementation. However, the Government also relies on organisations, as their agents, to implement regulations successfully for the intent to be achieved – a situation made more difficult because what organisations need to achieve is emergent, open to interpretation and often revised. There is a multiplier effect, with organisations required to implement a greater amount of regulations, post-GFC, at different stages of development. Involving a number of different regulatory agencies. This means organisations are not just dealing with one change initiative, but must consider what they can do to improve their success rate across a regulatory portfolio comprising multiple change initiatives. As a result of the unique challenges in this context, organisations face the difficulty of defining the success that, on the one hand, they want to achieve and, on the other hand, must achieve for an increasingly complex range of regulations.

The difficulty of defining success (and failure)

Organisations do choose different levels of activity when implementing regulations. This can range from the minimum compliance, generally more focussed on

keeping costs down, through to a more comprehensive approach to, for instance, creating a competitive advantage through compliance, or benefits for customers. This range of responses means that, from the organisation’s perspective, there can be different definitions of success, depending on the situation. To do the minimum to comply with a regulation, for one organisation, could be considered success. For another, aiming for a more comprehensive approach, achieving only the minimum level could be considered a failure. There can also be a temporal aspect to success, depending on what organisations want to achieve. With the increase in regulation post-GFC, near enough, or almost complying, may be considered a successful outcome, particularly if requirements are unclear. Typically, this level of activity would be a first step, with the intention to undertake additional implementation activities later, when operation of regulations is more established. Therefore, organisations choose the level of success they want to achieve; however, the definition may differ across organisations. But how does this variable response reconcile with what organisations must achieve?

Regulatory agencies have indicated expectations for genuine compliance that entails doing more than the minimum, or only technical compliance. It could, therefore, be concluded they would consider success means doing more than just complying with laws and regulations, and that anything less would be considered failure. However, a review of regulatory requirements indicates there may be situations, when this would not

be the case, and partial success may be acceptable. For instance, regulatory agencies can use transitional arrangements for regulations, creating a staged approach to implementation (ASIC 2011b). Partial compliance may also be acceptable, when there are new requirements and they want to take a more facilitative role, the design of regulations makes implementation difficult, or when the regulation is not working as expected (Lynch 2013). This reflects the reality that organisations can only do as well with regards to implementation as the design of the regulations allows, and that regulators can only provide guidance to the extent the law and associated regulations are clear in their operation. However, more can also be expected, because the minimum level for compliance can increase as the operations of the regulations are clarified.

Assessments of success can also differ between types of regulations managed by different regulatory agencies (APRA 2012b). Some can be more behavioural-focussed, concerned with black letter law, rules and penalties, while others can be more outcome or risk-based-focussed, concerned with principles and prevention. The tolerance for partial or staged success is likely to be lower for behavioural regulations, but higher for risk-based regulations. However, particularly if regulations have been in operation for some time, regulatory agencies may assess any actions that do not meet genuine compliance requirements as failure. This can occur if, in their view, the intended outcomes are being undermined by the organisation’s actions. Assessment of

failure would also occur if laws and regulations are broken, due to wilful or criminal non-compliance (ASIC 2012; Kehoe & Thompson 2013). Therefore, defining the success that must be achieved depends on how the regulatory agencies assess the organisation’s effort and intentions, the development stage and type of regulation and whether the regulations work appropriately in the view of the regulatory agencies.

As illustrated in Figure 2, combining the different views about what organisations want and need to achieve shows that success and failure are graduated and partially-overlapping bands of activity, rather than precise definitions. Two additional categories of below-minimum compliance are used, in addition to the levels of implementation activity suggested by Hackman (2009a, 2009b). On this expanded continuum, failure can range from Not Comply, through Partially Comply, to Comply, with the upper level reflecting the view of regulatory agencies that organisations should do more than the minimum. Success can range from Partially Comply, reflecting achievement of some success from either the organisation or regulatory agency view, with increasing levels of success when more activities are undertaken, through Do More to Do Extra. Any response below Partially Comply would be failure and above Comply would be success. However, in between these levels, there is an Overlapping Zone comprising Partially Comply and Comply, where assessments can be success or failure, depending on a range of factors, some of which might lie outside the organisation’s control.

Discussion

Given the dynamics involved in defining success and failure, it is not surprising organisations report experiencing mixed levels of success. There are many moving parts to consider, with three aspects of particular importance. Firstly, there is a level of ambiguity, with potentially subjective assessments of whether actions constitute success or failure at the more minimal levels of compliance. Secondly, as regulations mature in operation, the minimum level for compliance can increase. This means that what was the minimum previously can become partial compliance and potentially assessed as failure, rather than success. This shift in goal posts for minimum compliance can occur more than once during the lifetime of a regulation. Thirdly, organisations can, to an extent, choose what they consider to be success – dependent, for instance, on their operations, culture and aspirations.

The critical role of the board and senior executives to commit to and deliver compliance is reflected in the change in emphasis in the recently revised Australian Standard for Compliance.

The implication and interaction of these moving parts is that it may not be possible to have meaningful comparisons of success across organisations, except when compliance actions are defined clearly. This is unlikely to be satisfactory to organisations and regulators, when the focus for success is not only on implementing regulations, but also on achieving the intent of the regulations (Australasian Compliance Institute (ACI) 2009; APRA 2012b). Of concern, when considering Hackman's (2009a, 2009b) recent research, is evidence supporting the fact that organisations need to experience success before becoming more proactive in their next regulatory implementation. No doubt organisations do want to comply by implementing regulations appropriately, but continuing to experience mixed levels of success may reduce their enthusiasm, as well as make it harder for compliance professionals to argue for resources and to implement more than a reactive response. The danger here is that such

responses may fall into the Overlapping Zone, where there is ambiguity about the definitions for success and failure, thereby perpetuating, rather than improving, the current mixed experiences.

So is there anything organisations can do to improve their levels of success? One approach, based on the discussion of success and failure, could be to do more than the minimum to comply, for all regulations. This would raise the level of implementation for all regulations and avoid any ambiguity about the outcome. The disadvantage with this approach is that it could actually lead to lower levels of success because regulations differ not only in their duration and the complexity of change activities required, but also their operational maturity (Murray 2007; Hackman 2008; Mullins 2008). Higher levels of compliance activity may suit some more complex and operationally-mature regulations, but may not suit others, particularly when

requirements are still emerging, or being revised. So would it be better to do only the minimum for all regulations? Again, this approach may suit some regulations, but not others. Instead, differential effort across regulations, commensurate with their clarity of requirements and maturity, is likely to result in better use of resources and higher levels of success than using a one-size-fits-all or standardised approach.

To accommodate the changing requirements as regulations mature, organisations could

also plan regulatory projects to continue over a longer period, supported by appropriate change implementation activities (Hackman 2008). Current practice, particularly in larger organisations, tends to focus on instigating regulatory projects that conclude once a go-live date is achieved, with regulatory activities and subsequent changes handed to the business to manage. The mixed rates of success experienced by organisations could stem from assessments being made at this point, when it is unlikely that all aspects of regulatory operations have been clarified, or could be implemented effectively. Instead, success could be assessed progressively, as stages of the implementation are completed over a longer timeframe, reflecting a more realistic approach to measuring outcomes.

While these two suggestions could assist with improving the level of success, it is also clear, from the discussion of the dynamics impacting the

implementation of regulations, that there is no one right way to suit all situations. The need will always exist to take into account the history, complexity and the particular focus of the organisation's operations, in order to select the appropriate approach. Nevertheless, the insights presented in this discussion, particularly about the unique dynamic involved in assessments of success and failure, can assist compliance professionals to support the business to develop more targeted plans, the implementation of regulations and more appropriate allocation of resources over time, to achieve success appropriate to the organisation.

Conclusion

This article explored some of the many reasons why implementation of regulations in organisations is such a challenge. The concern is that organisations often report experiencing a mixed level of success, despite spending significant time and financial resources on regulatory projects and compliance activities. So what can organisations do differently? Using a change management lens, this article highlighted the unique dynamics involved with implementation of regulations, particularly their emergent nature and potential variations in definitions for success and failure. Two suggestions are offered to assist with improving success: use of a differentiated approach to manage regulations and implementation projects planned over a longer timeframe, to accommodate the evolution of regulations. In addition, awareness of how these unique dynamics operate can assist compliance professionals to argue for tailored approaches to implementing regulations for their organisation and to support the business in achieving improved levels of success. ❖

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